

WATER PROTECTION AREAS AND RIPARIAN BUFFERS WITHIN THE CAMENCA AND CUBOLTA RIVER BASINS

Zone de protecție a apei și tampone ripariale din Camenca și Cubolta

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Summary. Present study is a first attempt to perform a digital delineation of the protection areas and riparian buffer strips for the rivers and reservoirs for the Camenca and Cubolta rivers and their tributaries. Also, a special attention was paid to estimation of main land cover types in the limits of riparian buffer strips. Delineation of protection areas and riparian buffer strips was done using recommendations from national legislation, Water Law, and geoinformational techniques in semiautomat way. Land cover was evaluated by using actual satellite images from Google Earth tool. Main river types considered are streams, 2,5-10 km, very small streams, 10-50 km, small rivers, 50-100 km, medium rivers, 100-200 km. As a result, 267,4 km² and 334 km² of water protection areas were delimited in the Cubolta river and the Camenca river basins. These areas are divided between medium and very small rivers, with a share of 30-39% and 57-66% respectively. 29 km² and 36,5 km² of riparian buffer strips were delineated for the two study areas. The share of these areas, in both basins, is divided approximately equal between streams, very small rivers and medium rivers. In the Cubolta and the Camenca river, no small rivers, with the length between 50-100 km, were identified. The areas along medium, very small rivers as well as streams are mainly covered by grassland, by 60-84%, forests are practically absent, of about 2-9%. Rural and arable areas are not high of 2-13%, being lower in Camenca basin and higher in Cubolta basin.

Key words: riparian buffers strips, land cover, small rivers

INTRODUCTION. One of the important measures in order to protect water bodies is enlargement of areas requiring special protection – protection areas. From this category, two environmental areas represent an important interest: water protection areas and riparian buffer strips. Both are areas situated in close proximity of the banks of rivers and water accumulations. Both types of areas have the aim to prevent effects of human activities on waters, being considered regions with special water protection. In both areas, a special regime of economic activity is installed. Many researches¹ focus on importance of riparian

¹ *Buffer strips and hedges*, In: NWRM, 2013 <http://nwrn.eu/measure/buffer-strips-and-hedges>, http://nwrn.eu/sites/default/files/nwrn_ressources/a2_-_buffer_strips_and_hedges.pdf (accessed on 20.04.2023); *Establishment and restoration of riparian buffers*, 2023 <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/establishment-and-restoration-of-riparian-buffer-s> (accessed on 14.01.2023); Cole L. J., Stockan J., Helliwell R. *Managing riparian buffer strips to optimise ecosystem services: A review*, In: Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Volume 296, 106891, 2020. 65 p. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891> (accessed on 20.04.2023).

buffer strips for protection both rivers as well as ecosystems and soils. Riparian buffer strips represent green barriers between waters and areas used for different economic needs, especially for agriculture. Multifunctionality of these environmental areas is evident: prevention of biodiversity loss, surface status deterioration, protection of ecosystems and increase of ecosystem services, reduce flood risk, increase the sustainability of agriculture, filtration of chemicals and nutrients use in agriculture (nitrates, phosphorus etc.), reduction of erosion and sediments, regulation of microclimate by cooling ensuring, drought mitigation etc.². Many studies mention that riparian buffer strips are effective in different pollutants reductions: herbicide transport reduction by 27%³, removal up to 92% of nitrate⁴, diminution of nitrate nitrogen by 33% in surface runoff and by 70% in groundwater⁵ etc. Another significant role of riparian buffer strips is their shape, being natural corridors for distribution of species of the animal and plant kingdom. Longitudinal connectivity is particularly important for dispersal of species across temperature gradients, while lateral connectivity allows heterogeneous microclimates that help species cope with fluctuating weather⁶. Even if riparian buffer strips have evident benefits, there are also risks regarding them. Thus, under high nutrient loadings, these can become saturated and act as a source of pollutants, limiting their long-term effectiveness⁷. In these conditions, sustainable management and in time monitoring are important to be implemented in order to protect waters by applying this measure.

² *Buffer strips and hedges*, In: NWRM, 2013 <http://nwrn.eu/measure/buffer-strips-and-hedges>, http://nwrn.eu/sites/default/files/nwrn_ressources/a2_-_buffer_strips_and_hedges.pdf (accessed on 20.04.2023); *Establishment and restoration of riparian buffers*, 2023 <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/establishment-and-restoration-of-riparian-buffer-s> (accessed on 14.01.2023); Cole L. J., Stockan J., Helliwell R. *Managing riparian buffer strips to optimise ecosystem services: A review*, In: Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Volume 296, 106891, 2020. 65 p. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891> (accessed on 20.04.2023); Englund O., Börjesson P., Mola-Yudego B. et al. *Strategic deployment of riparian buffers and windbreaks in Europe can co-deliver biomass and environmental benefits*. In: Commun Earth Environ 2, 2021, 176 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-021-00247-y> (accessed on 14.01.2023); Stutter M., Kronvang B., Huallacháin D. and Rozemeijer J. *Current Insights into the Effectiveness of Riparian Management, Attainment of Multiple Benefits, and Potential Technical Enhancements*. In: J. Environ. Qual., 48, 2019 236-247. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2019.01.0020> (accessed on 14.01.2023); Haddaway N.R., Brown C., Eales J. et al. *The multifunctional roles of vegetated strips around and within agricultural fields*. In: Environ Evid 7, 2018, 14 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-018-0126-2> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

³ Krutz L.J., Senseman S.A., Zablotowicz R.M., Matcocha M.A., *Reducing herbicide runoff from agricultural fields with vegetative filter strips: a review*. In: Weed Sci., 53(3), 2005, 353-367.

⁴ Cavallito M. *Riparian buffer strips reduce water pollution while protecting soil health, study says*, 2022. <https://resoilfoundation.org/en/environment/riparian-buffer-strips-water/> (accessed on 14.01.2023);

⁵ Valkama E., Usva K., Saarinen M., Uusi-Kämpä, J. 2019 A Meta-Analysis on Nitrogen Retention by Buffer Zones. J. Environ. Qual., 48: 270-279. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2018.03.0120> (accessed on 14.01.2023).

⁶ *Establishment and restoration of riparian buffers*, 2023 <https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/metadata/adaptation-options/establishment-and-restoration-of-riparian-buffer-s> (accessed on 14.01.2023);

⁷ Cole L. J., Stockan J., Helliwell R. *Managing riparian buffer strips to optimise ecosystem services: A review*, In: Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment, Volume 296, 106891, 2020. 65 p. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891> (accessed on 20.04.2023);

Riparian buffer strips are formed usually from wooded and grassy vegetation. Comparing these two types of vegetation, both have different impact of protection management. Wooded buffers are more efficient at reducing nitrate-nitrogen in shallow ground water but less efficient at reducing phosphates⁸, these can contribute to natural water and flood management, slowing the flow of water from the land into receiving water bodies by increasing infiltration, reducing flow velocity and providing temporary water storage⁹. Also, when compared to vegetated buffers, wooded buffers support more native plant species¹⁰, and provide undisturbed habitats favouring woodland beetles¹¹ and insectivorous mammals¹². From the other hand, grassy buffers are more effective at slowing the flow of water, increasing their ability to intercept sediments, nutrients and other contaminants¹³. The differential uptake and retention of contaminants by forested and vegetated buffers indicates that zoned buffer strips, consisting of a strip of trees and a strip of grassy or herbaceous vegetation, are likely to be best at mitigating diffuse pollution¹⁴.

In the Republic of Moldova, delimitation of *riparian protection area of rivers* as well as

⁸ Osborne L., Kovacic D., *Riparian vegetated buffer strips in water-quality restoration and stream management*. In: *Freshwater Biol.*, 29, 1993, 243–258 doi:10.1016/0006-3207(95)90078-0 (accessed on 14.01.2023);

⁹ Dixon S., Sear D.A., Sykes T., Odoni N., *The effects of floodplain forest restoration and log-jams on flood risk and flood hydrology*. In: *EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (Vol. 17)*. 2015. doi:10.1002/esp.3919 (accessed on 14.01.2023); Tabacchi E., Lambs L., Guillooy H., Planty-Tabacchi A.M., Muller E., Décamps H., *Impacts of riparian vegetation on hydrological processes*. In: *Hydrol. Process.*, 14(16–17), 2000, 2959–2976. doi:10.1002/1099-1085200011/12)14 (accessed on 14.01.2023).

¹⁰ Paine L.K., Ribic C.A. 2002. *Comparison of riparian plant communities under four land management systems in southwestern Wisconsin*. In: *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ* 92(491), 93–105.

¹¹ Stockan J.A., Baird J., Langan S.J., Young M.R., Iason G.R. *Effects of riparian buffer strips on ground beetles (Coleoptera, Carabidae) within an agricultural landscape*. In: *Insect Conserv. Diver.*, 7(2), 2014, 172–184. doi:10.1111/icad.12043 (accessed on 14.01.2023).

¹² Maisonneuve C., Rioux S., *Importance of riparian habitats for small mammal and herpetofaunal communities in agricultural landscapes of southern Québec*. In: *Agr. Ecosyst. Environ.*, 83(1–2), 2001, 165–175. doi:10.1016/S0167-8809(00)00259-0 (accessed on 14.01.2023);

¹³ Osborne L., Kovacic D., *Riparian vegetated buffer strips in water-quality restoration and stream management*. In: *Freshwater Biol.*, 29, 1993, 243–258 doi:10.1016/0006-3207(95)90078-0 (accessed on 14.01.2023); Erktan A., Cécillon L., Roose E., Lacoste F., N., Rey, F., *Morphological diversity of plant barriers does not increase sediment retention in eroded marly gullies under ecological restoration*. In: *Plant Soil*, 370(1-2), 2013, 653-669; Knight K.W., Schultz R.C., Mabry C.M., Isenhardt T.M. *Ability of remnant riparian forests, with and without grass filters, to buffer concentrated surface runoff*. In: *J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.*, 46(2), 2010, 311–322. doi:10.1111/j.1752-1688.2010.00422.x (accessed on 14.01.2023); Lin C.H., Lerch R.N., Goynes K.W., Garrett H.E., *Reducing herbicides and veterinary antibiotics losses from agroecosystems using vegetative buffers*. In: *J. Environ. Qual.*, 40(3), 2011, 791-799.

¹⁴ Cole L. J., Stockan J., Helliwell R. *Managing riparian buffer strips to optimise ecosystem services: A review*. In: *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment*, Volume 296, 106891, 2020. 65 p. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106891> (accessed on 20.04.2023); Valkama E., Usva K., Saarinen M., Uusi-Kämpä, J. *A Meta-Analysis on Nitrogen Retention by Buffer Zones*. *J. Environ.* In: *Qual.*, 48, 2019, 270-279. <https://doi.org/10.2134/jeq2018.03.0120> (accessed on 14.01.2023); Knight K.W., Schultz R.C., Mabry C.M., Isenhardt T.M. *Ability of remnant riparian forests, with and without grass filters, to buffer concentrated surface runoff*. In: *J. Am. Water Resour. Assoc.*, 46(2), 2010, 311–322. doi:10.1111/j.1752-1688.2010.00422.x (accessed on 14.01.2023).

riparian buffer strips as a measure to protect water bodies is included in the two national river basin management plans¹⁵. In this context, the aim of the study is delimitation of this type of areas using geoinformation technologies, as well as evaluation of land cover in the established limits. Main objectives are i) definition of dimensions of water protection areas and riparian buffer strips ii) calculation and mapping of surfaces of these environmental areas iii) estimation of land cover types within the limits of the water protection areas and riparian buffer strips.

STUDY AREA

Present research focuses on two study areas: Cubolta river basin and Camenca river basin. Both basins are situated in the northern part of the Republic of Moldova. Cubolta river is positioned in the limits of the Dniester basin, being one of the main tributaries of Raut river. The river network is of 590 km, from which the Cubolta river has a length of 109 km or 18,5% of total, rivers of 2-10km - 318,6 km or 54%, rivers of 10-20 km - 161,6 km or 27,4%. There are no rivers with length between 20 km and 100 km. Density of river network is 0.63 km/km². The area of river basin is about 939 km², the shape is prolonged, left and right part of the basin being approximately equal (fig. 1).

The Camenca river is one of the main tributaries of the Prut river. Main tributaries of Camenca river are *Șovățul Mic*, *Căldărușa*, *Glodeanca*, *Șovățul Mare*, *Camencuța*, which length is between 20 and 50 km. River network is about 737,5 km from which, the Camenca is about 113 km or 15,3%, rivers of 2-10km - 389,5 km or 52,8%, rivers of 10-50 km - 234,9 km or 31,85%. There are no rivers with length between 50 km and 100 km. Density of river network is 0.60 km/km². The area of river basin is about 1239 km², the shape is prolonged, however left part of the basin is much bigger than the right part (fig. 2).

In both basins, main land use is agriculture covering over 60% of the basin. Other land cover types are settlements, forests, grassland which cover up to 10-20% of the basin.

The Cubolta river discharge is about 1.65 m³/s, volume of 53 mil.m³. The Camenca river discharge is of 1,30 m³/s, with a volume of 41 mil.m³. Main water resources of both rivers are formed during spring and pluvial floods in spring and summer, low flows are specific for summer-autumn and winter seasons.

METHODS AND MATERIALS

In the Republic of Moldova, main law that refers to river protection area and buffer strips is *Water Law No. 272 of 23.12.2011*¹⁶ Main concepts refer to:

- *protection area of rivers and water accumulations* – the territory related to water body with established dimensions, intended for the protection of surface waters against pollution, depletion and siltation;
- *riparian buffer strips* – the territory with established dimensions within protection areas intended for development of forest or grassland;

¹⁵ Hotărârea de Guvern al Republicii Moldova nr. 444 din 29.06.2022 cu privire la aprobarea Programului de gestionare a districtului bazinului hidrografic Dunarea-Prut si Marea Neagra https://www.legis.md/cautare/getResults?doc_id=132734&lang=ro; Hotărârea de Guvern al Republicii Moldova nr. 814 din 17.10.2017 cu privire la aprobarea Planul de gestionare a districtului bazinului hidrografic Nistru <http://lex.justice.md/index.php?action=view&view=doc&lang=1&id=371992>

¹⁶ Parlamentul Republicii Moldova, Lege apelor nr. 272 din 23.12.2011 cu https://www.legis.md/cautare/getResults?doc_id=141217&lang=ro# (accessed on 26.01.2024);

• *forest curtain for bank protection* – the forest curtain along the banks of the water bodies intended for their protection against erosion and landslides.

Also, the *Water Law No. 272 of 23.12.2011* clearly regulates dimensions of *riparian buffer strips* and *forest curtains for bank protection*.

Figure 1. Cubolta river basin

Figure 2. Camenca river basin

Table 1. Dimensions of environmental areas

Type of river	River length, km	Width of, m		
		Protection area	Buffer strip	Forest curtain for bank protection
Streams	2,5 - 10	15	5	15 - convex and straight banks 20 - concave banks
Very small rivers	10 – 50	500	20	15 - convex and straight banks 20 - concave banks
Small rivers	50 – 100	500	20	20 - convex and straight banks 30 - concave banks
Medium rivers	100 – 200	500	50	30 - convex and straight banks 50 - concave banks
Large rivers	Prut, Dni-ester	1000	100	40 - convex and straight banks 70 - concave banks

Source: Water Law nr. 272 of 23.12.2011

In order to delimitate water protection areas and riparian buffer strips, Quantum GIS¹⁷ was utilized. Main river network was extracted from National geospatial data fund, geopor-

¹⁷ Quantum GIS 3.30, 2023, <https://www.qgis.org/en/site/forusers/download.html> (accessed on 14.01.2023);

River basins	Dimension of protection areas, km ²					Dimension of riparian buffer strips, km ²				
	Streams	Very small rivers	Small rivers	Medium river	Total	Streams	Very small rivers	Small rivers	Medium river	Total
Cubolta	9,24	153,4	0	105	267,4	11,2	6,69	0	11,2	29,0
Căldărușa*	3,82	84,9	0	0	88,6	2,89	3,93	0	0	6,78
Șovățul Mare*	1,49	42,3	0	0	43,8	2,4	1,88	0	0	4,3
Șovățul Mic*	2,69	62,6	0	0	65,3	2,6	2,93	0	0	5,56
Camenca, total	12,4	221	0	100	334	12,5	10,2	0	13,8	36,5

Table 2. The results of delimitation of water protection areas and riparian buffer strips
* tributaries of the Camenca river

Figure 4. Distribution of the areas of riparian buffer strips according to the river types in the Cubolta river basin (left) and the Camenca river basin (right)

In the Camenca river basin, the share of riparian buffer strips areas distributed by river type is also similar to the one from the Cubolta basin. From the total area, 38% of the area was delineated along Camenca river – as a medium river, 28% – along very small rivers, and only 34% – along streams. In the Căldărușa, the Șovățul Mare basins and the Șovățul Mic, riparian buffer strips areas are 6,78 km², 4,3 km², 5,56 km². Overall, about 44-58% of the area was evaluated for very small rivers, and 43-56% for streams (fig. 4, tab. 2.).

Land cover in the limits of riparian buffer strips

Riparian buffer strips are considered to be covered by natural vegetation. In order to evaluate the real situation of the land cover in the limits of these areas, actual satellites images were analyzed, land cover was extracted and generalized.

Distribution of land cover types in the limits of riparian buffers of the rivers and water accumulation from the Camenca and Cubolta rivers basins are shown in the figures 5, 6, the share being presented in the figures 7-9.

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As it can be observed from the figures 7-9, the largest territories are covered by grassland all types of rivers in both basins. The Cubolta river and its reservoirs are surrounded by grassland with a share of 63%, shrubs and forest cover only 4% and 2%, rural area and agriculture are 13% and 11%. The share of grassland increases by 10% in the limits of riparian buffer strips of very small rivers and their reservoirs, reaching 70% of the total. However, shrubs and forests area are also higher as in case of Cubolta, being 5% and 8%. Rural and arable lands are lower, equal to 5% and 9%. Main land cover along the streams is grassland of about 80%. Shrubs, forest, arable and rural lands occupy small territories, about 3-6%. Overall, at basinal level, riparian buffer strips are formed by 71% grassland, 4% shrubs, forests, wetlands each, 9% rural and 8% arable area.

In the Camenca river basin, situation with the land cover in the limits of the riparian buffer strips is the same as in the Cubolta river, over 78% of the area being grasslands, 2-5% are covered by shrubs and forests, 4-5% – by rural and arable area, and 6% – by wetlands. Along the Camenca river, the riparian buffer strips area is covered by grassland 70%, other categories being forest, 9%, shrubs, 1%, rural and arable area 8% each. In case of very small

rivers the share of grassland is higher, being 79%, which is followed by wetlands, by 10%, mainly due to degradation of the big number of reservoirs situated on the courses. Other land cover types are of 2-4%. The highest share of grassland is observed in the limits of streams from Camenca basin, by 84%. Very few territories are occupied by forests, shrubs, wetlands, rural and arable area.

tal.md¹⁸, land cover types from the limits of considered environmental areas were digitized from satellite images from Google Earth 7.3.6¹⁹ and classified in the following classes: urban and rural settlements, grassland, shrubs, forest, arable area, vineyards, orchards and wetlands.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Water protection areas and riparian buffer strips limits

Delimitation of water protection areas and riparian buffer strips limits was done for rivers as well as for reservoirs situated on their courses. As a result, 267,4 km² and 334 km² of water protection areas were delimited in the Cubolta river and the Camenca river basins.

In the Cubolta river, from total area of protection areas, 39% of the area was delineated along Cubolta river – as a medium river, 57% – along very small rivers, and only 4% – along streams (fig. 3, tab. 2.).

Figure 3. Distribution of water protection areas according to the river types in the Cubolta river basin (left) and the Camenca river basin (right)

In the Camenca river basin, the share of water protection areas distributed by river type is similar to the one from the Cubolta basin. From the total area, 30% of the area was delineated along Camenca river – as a medium river, 66% – along very small rivers, and only 4% – along streams. In the basins of Camenca tributaries: the Căldărușa, the Șovățul Mare and the Șovățul Mic, delineated areas are 88,6 km², 43,8 km², 65,3 km². Overall, about 96% of the area was evaluated for very small rivers, and 4% for streams (fig. 3, tab. 2.).

Taking into account the fact that the limits of the riparian buffer strips and forest curtain for bank protection differ insignificantly (tab. 1), the delimitation was carried out by combining the dimensions as follows: streams and very small streams – 20 m., small rivers – 30 m., medium rivers – 50 m. As a result, 29 km² and 36,5 km² of riparian buffer strips were estimated for the two basins (the Cubolta and the Camenca basins).

In the Cubolta river, from total area of riparian buffer strips, 39% of the area was delineated along Cubolta river – as a medium river, 23% – along very small rivers, and 38% – along streams (fig. 4, tab. 2.).

¹⁸ National geospatial data fund, geoportal.md, 2023 (NGDF) www.geoportal.md. (accessed on 14.01.2023);

¹⁹ Google Earth 7.3.6. (2020). North Development Region of the Republic of Moldova. 47°56'58.19" N, 27°54'12.27" E, Landsat / Copernicus, CNES / Airbus, <https://www.google.com/earth/versions/> (accessed on 2.01.2023)

Figure 5. Land cover types of riparian buffer strips in the Cubolta basin

Figure 6. Land cover types of riparian buffer strips in the Camenca basin

Figure 7. Land cover types in the limits of riparian buffer strips of the Cubolta river, very small rivers and streams, Cubolta basin

Figure 8. Land cover types in the limits of riparian buffer strips of the Camenca river, very small rivers and stream, Camenca basin

Figure 9. Land cover types in the limits of riparian buffer strips of the Cubolta basin (left) and the Camenca river basin (right)

CONCLUSION

Present study is a first attempt to perform a digital delineation of the protection areas and riparian buffer strips for the rivers and reservoirs for the Camenca and Cubolta rivers and their tributaries. As a result, 267,4 km² and 334 km² of water protection areas were delimited in the Cubolta river and the Camenca river basins. These areas are divided between medium and very small rivers, with a share of 30-39% and 57-66% respectively. Limits for the riparian buffer strips and forest curtain for bank protection were considered the same due to the fact that national legislation does not provide big differences between these areas. Thus, 29 km² and 36,5 km² of riparian buffer strips were delineated for the two study areas. The share of these areas in both basins is divided approximately equal between streams, very small rivers and medium rivers. In the Cubolta and the Camenca river, no small rivers, with the length between 50-100 km, were identified.

Of a high interest is evaluation of land cover in the limits of riparian buffer strips. The areas along medium, very small rivers as well as streams are mainly covered by grassland, by 60-84%, forests are practically absent, of about 2-9%. Rural and arable areas are not high of 2-13%, being lower in the Camenca basin and higher in the Cubolta basin.

As zoned riparian buffer formed by rows of grassland and forest represent the best management practices in order to reduce human impact and improve environmental status, it is

important to increase the area covered by forests in the limits of riparian buffers. The species to be planted on bank of rivers and water accumulations, in order to increase forest areas, are: basic: *Quercus* (different types), *Robinia pseudoacacia*, *Gleditsia triacanthos*, *Sophora japonica* L., *Ulmus pumila*, *Pinus nigra*, *Juglans regia*; mixed species: *Acer platanoides*, *Tilia* (different species), *Acer campestre*, *Malus Sylvestris*, *Prunus serotina*, *Elaeagnus angustifolia*, *Acer tataricum*, *Prunus mahaleb*, *Prunus avium*, *Pyrus pyraster*, *Prunus divaricate*, *Acer saccharum*, *Sorbus aucuparia*, *Sorbus domestica*, *Armeniaca vulgaris*; shrubs: *Sambucus nigra*, *Maclura pomifera*, *Crataegus monogyna*, *Ligustrum vulgare*, *Viburnum lantana*, *Corylus avellane*, *Cotinus coggygria*, *Syringa vulgaris*, etc.²⁰

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²⁰ Galupa D. *Înființarea perdelelor forestiere de protecție în calitate de măsură de adaptare la schimbările climatice: Ghid practic pentru producătorii agricoli*. Chișinău: Tipogr. „Bons Offices”, 2021. 60 p.